

A Deletion Algorithm for the Combinatorial Weights of Scalar Feynman Diagrams

Göktürk Üçoluk*

1983

Revised version, 2026

Abstract

A simple deletion algorithm is described for computing the combinatorial weight of a given Feynman diagram for a real scalar field. The diagram is assumed to be already given; the problem considered here is not the evaluation of the corresponding amplitude, but the counting of the distinct half-line sewings which produce the same diagram under the stated conventions. The procedure removes external lines, self-loops, and vertex-to-vertex lines successively, multiplying the local factors obtained at each step. Special care is required when several self-loops are incident on the same vertex, since these loops are not ordered.

Historical note. This is a revised version of an unpublished note written in 1983. The notation and terminology have been adjusted for clarity, while the result is kept in its original constructive form.

1 Introduction

A Feynman diagram consists of vertices and connections between them. In this note we consider diagrams corresponding to a real scalar field, or equivalently to self-conjugate scalar particles. The diagram itself is assumed to have already been drawn. We do not discuss here how the diagram is generated, nor do we discuss the evaluation of the corresponding integral or amplitude.

The problem considered is the following. Given a diagram with prescribed vertices and connections, count the number of different ways in which the half-lines at the vertices can be sewn together so as to produce that diagram. This number will be called the *combinatorial weight* of the diagram. It is closely related to the usual symmetry-factor problem, but the present formulation is constructive: the weight is obtained by deleting the connections of the diagram and multiplying the corresponding local factors.

Throughout the note, the vertices of the given diagram are regarded as distinguishable. External end-connections are also regarded as distinguishable unless stated otherwise. Multiple internal lines between the same two vertices, and multiple self-loops at the same vertex, are not ordered.

2 Definitions

The procedure is a connection-deletion procedure. Three kinds of connections are used.

End-connection. A connection corresponding to an incoming or outgoing external particle.

Loop-connection. A connection which starts at a vertex and ends at the same vertex.

*Permanent address: Department of Computer Engineering, Middle East Technical University, Ankara, Türkiye.

Vertex-to-vertex connection. A connection which starts at one vertex and ends at another vertex.

To delete a connection means to erase the curve representing that connection from the diagram. After a deletion, the degrees of the affected vertices are reduced accordingly.

At any stage of the algorithm, the *degree* of a vertex is the number of half-lines still incident on that vertex. Thus the degree used in a deletion factor is always the degree immediately before that deletion is performed.

For example, consider the diagram:

Before the deletion, the degrees of the three vertices are

vertex	degree
1	4
2	4
3	4

If connection α is deleted from the diagram, the result is:

The new degrees are

vertex	degree
1	3
2	3
3	4.

3 The Algorithm

The combinatorial weight is obtained as a product of factors introduced during the deletion of the connections.

1. **End-connections.** If an end-connection is deleted from a vertex of degree M , introduce the factor

$$M.$$

2. **Loop-connections.** If a single loop-connection is deleted from a vertex of degree M , introduce the factor

$$\binom{M}{2}.$$

More generally, if r loop-connections are incident on the same vertex of degree M and are deleted as a group, introduce the factor

$$L(M, r) = \frac{M!}{(M - 2r)! 2^r r!}.$$

This grouped form is necessary because the r self-loops are not ordered. Equivalently, it is the number of ways of choosing $2r$ half-lines at the vertex and partitioning them into r unordered pairs.

3. **Vertex-to-vertex connections.** Suppose two vertices μ and ν have degrees M and N , respectively, immediately before the deletion. Suppose further that there are i connections between these two vertices, and that j of these i connections are to be deleted. Then introduce the factor

$$f(M, N, i, j) = j! \binom{M}{j} \binom{N}{j} \binom{i}{j}^{-1}.$$

Equivalently,

$$f(M, N, i, j) = \frac{M!N!(i-j)!}{(M-j)!(N-j)!i!}.$$

4. The deletion may be performed in any order, provided that the degrees and multiplicities used in the above formulae are those present immediately before the corresponding deletion. Identical self-loops at the same vertex should be treated collectively, or else the corresponding factorial correction must be included.

4 Proof of the Deletion Factors

We prove the factors used in the algorithm by counting possible sewings of labelled half-lines.

4.1 End-connections

If a vertex has degree M , then a distinguishable external end-connection may be attached to any one of the M half-lines at that vertex. Hence deleting such an end-connection contributes the factor M .

4.2 Loop-connections

If a vertex has degree M , then a single self-loop is formed by choosing two of the M half-lines and sewing them together. Since the order of the two half-lines is irrelevant, the number of possibilities is

$$\binom{M}{2}.$$

If r self-loops are incident on the same vertex, then $2r$ half-lines must be chosen and divided into r unordered pairs. The number of such pairings is

$$L(M, r) = \frac{M!}{(M-2r)!2^r r!}.$$

The factor 2^r removes the ordering inside each pair, and the factor $r!$ removes the ordering of the r loop-connections themselves.

For example, at a ϕ^4 vertex carrying two self-loops one obtains

$$L(4, 2) = \frac{4!}{0!2^2 2!} = 3.$$

The three possible pairings of four half-lines are

$$(12)(34), \quad (13)(24), \quad (14)(23).$$

A successive application of the single-loop factor would give

$$\binom{4}{2} \binom{2}{2} = 6,$$

which counts the two identical loops in both possible orders. The division by $2!$ is therefore essential.

4.3 Vertex-to-vertex connections

Consider two vertices μ and ν of degrees M and N . Assume that i connections are present between them. First consider the case in which all i of these connections are deleted.

Label the half-lines at the two vertices by

$$\mathcal{M} = \{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_M\}, \quad \mathcal{N} = \{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_N\}.$$

To form i connections, choose i half-lines at the first vertex, choose i half-lines at the second vertex, and pair the two chosen sets. This gives

$$\binom{M}{i} \binom{N}{i} i! = \frac{M!N!}{(M-i)!(N-i)!i!}$$

possibilities. The factor $i!$ pairs the two chosen i -element sets; the connections themselves are not ordered.

Now consider the more general case in which only j of the i connections between μ and ν are deleted. Let the corresponding factor be $f(M, N, i, j)$. If $j = i$, the preceding result gives

$$f(M, N, i, i) = \frac{M!N!}{(M-i)!(N-i)!i!}.$$

Moreover, two successive partial deletions must give the same result as one deletion of the combined size. Hence

$$f(M, N, i, j_1 + j_2) = f(M, N, i, j_1) f(M - j_1, N - j_1, i - j_1, j_2).$$

The number of ordered choices of j half-lines from the first vertex and j half-lines from the second vertex is

$$\frac{M!N!}{(M-j)!(N-j)!}.$$

The correction for internal ordering depends only on i and j , not on M and N . We therefore write

$$f(M, N, i, j) = \frac{M!N!}{(M-j)!(N-j)!} g(i, j).$$

The condition for $j = i$ gives

$$g(i, i) = \frac{1}{i!}.$$

The consistency condition for two successive deletions gives

$$g(i, j_1 + j_2) = g(i, j_1) g(i - j_1, j_2).$$

Setting $i = j_1 + j_2$ yields

$$\frac{1}{i!} = g(i, j_1) \frac{1}{(i - j_1)!},$$

and therefore

$$g(i, j) = \frac{(i-j)!}{i!}.$$

Consequently,

$$f(M, N, i, j) = \frac{M!N!(i-j)!}{(M-j)!(N-j)!i!}.$$

This may also be written as

$$f(M, N, i, j) = j! \binom{M}{j} \binom{N}{j} \binom{i}{j}^{-1}.$$

5 Remarks on Symmetry Factors

The number obtained by the above algorithm is a combinatorial multiplicity of half-line sewings for the fixed diagram under the stated conventions. In the usual perturbative expansion this multiplicity combines with the factorials coming from the expansion of the exponential and from the interaction terms in the Lagrangian. Depending on these conventions, the final coefficient of a diagram is often expressed in terms of the reciprocal of a symmetry factor.

Thus the present algorithm should not be read by itself as a prescription for the full numerical coefficient of an amplitude. Rather, it computes the combinatorial part associated with constructing the given diagram from labelled half-lines. To compare with a conventionally quoted symmetry factor, one must also specify the normalization of the interaction term, the labelling of external lines, and whether indistinguishable vertices of the same type are divided out.

6 Conclusion

The deletion procedure gives a local method for computing the combinatorial weight of a scalar Feynman diagram once the diagram and the above labelling conventions have been fixed. End-connections, self-loops, and vertex-to-vertex connections each contribute a simple factor determined by the degrees and multiplicities present at the moment of deletion. The only special point is that several self-loops at the same vertex must be treated as an unordered collection; this produces the factor $1/r!$ in the loop formula.